

ROBUST

CRISIS GOVERNANCE IN TURBULENT TIMES

Societal Intelligence in Robust Crises Governance: Evidence from Nine European Countries and the EU

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Introduction

How did interactions between different types of knowledge develop during the COVID-19 pandemic at the national and European level? And how did these interactions contribute to the robust governance of the crisis? Societal intelligence – defined as *the capacity to make decisions informed by different types of knowledge whose epistemology is identifiable by the actors involved* – allows us to take a knowledge approach to crisis governance, considering not only the science-policy, but also the citizen-policy nexus simultaneously, thus looking at the triad of politics, expertise, and lifeworld knowledge.

Expanding the research focus on expertise in crisis governance and the science-policy interface, employing societal intelligence allows us to look into whether lifeworld knowledge was consulted and contributed to policymaking during the crisis, and which combinations of knowledge and actors yield the most robust governance solutions. Citizens, private, companies, trade unions, local community organizations and other civil society actors often complained that they had little or no say in the political decisions and interventions dramatically affecting their lives. The frequent failure to pay attention to citizen concerns during the pandemic led to substantial public demonstrations and even physical threats against politicians or experts. The lack of inclusion of lifeworld knowledge brought to the table by civil society representatives may have hampered robust governance solutions.

Societal intelligence's foundation lies in fact in the idea that not only there is three types of knowledge to take into account – political, expert, and lifeworld knowledge – but also that each actor can possess different types of knowledge, and is going to apply this knowledge in the decisions they take every day, from e.g., wearing a facemask to go get vaccinated.

This knowledge base expands as different types of knowledge and diverse actors interact, in what we call here interfaces. Interfaces are “social processes which encompass relations between scientists and other actors in the policy process, and which allow for exchanges, co-evolution, and joint construction of knowledge with the aim of enriching decision-making” (van den Hove 2007, p.815). This comparative analysis will thus look at the interfaces that allowed for interaction and knowledge exchange during the COVID-19 crisis, and whether this interaction and exchange led to the development of societal intelligence and robust governance solutions.

In order to carry out this analysis, societal intelligence has been operationalized in the following conditions: inclusivity, productive contestation, self-efficacy, intensity, and adaptability. These conditions are relevant to the study of societal intelligence both in normal times and in times of crisis. Turbulence such as the one created by the COVID-19 pandemic can in fact provide both a window of opportunity for new strategies and add challenges to these conditions for societal intelligence. In addition, such operationalization allows for the transition from the theoretical findings and constructs of D5.1 to the empirical application of societal intelligence in empirical data, evaluating crisis responses and their robustness.

As highlighted in the research question that opened this introduction, this analysis will focus both on the national and the European level of governance. At the national level, reports from the country teams have been analyzed to unpack patterns and innovations in the development and use of societal intelligence in national, regional, and local knowledge interfaces. At the European level, this analysis narrows down the scope by concentrating on EU decentralized agencies as knowledge interfaces. The two considered in this analysis will be the European Medicines Agency (EMA) and the European Center for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC), as their issue focus is directly related to the management of COVID-19.

This deliverable is structured as follows. After elaborating on the methodology, the following section will present in detail the conditions underlying societal intelligence, which are inclusivity, productive contestation, self-efficacy, intensity, and adaptability. Next, national level responses to the COVID-19 crisis are analyzed through these conditions, elaborating on successful robust

governance configurations at the national level. The section that follows delves into EU level responses to the pandemic, analyzing the EMA and ECDC and the integration of health policy at the supranational level. Finally, the conclusive section will summarize the findings, discuss the lessons drawn and discuss the implications for robustness from the perspective of negotiated societal intelligence.

Methodology

This deliverable relies on insights from empirical evidence on societal intelligence from nine European countries (Belgium, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Hungary, Italy, the Netherlands, Norway, and Spain) and the EU. This was complemented by secondary data drawn from public administration, crisis, and knowledge management literature.

The primary emphasis for the data collection has been on the COVID-19 pandemic, which represented a similar existential threat to all of the partner countries, enabling to analyse variations in differing administrative systems. Furthermore, the recency of the COVID-19 pandemic provided opportunities for primary data collection with stakeholders reflecting on the recent experience of the crisis. This enables deeper insight towards cross-organisational dynamics, which is more difficult to capture with the refugee but especially with the financial crisis, with limitations regarding institutional memory amongst both practitioners and scholars.

The data collection process was coordinated amongst the leads of WP3-5 through a joint 22-page data gathering template, which was developed in collaboration with all the partners to incorporate the flexibility for the idiosyncrasies of the different administrative contexts. The development of the template built on the conceptualisation of both dependent and independent variables of the ROBUST project outlined in D2.1, D3.1, D4.1 and D5.1. The template consisted of three core parts across the three crises under study:

1. Information on the crisis and response (pre-crisis preparedness, turbulence during crisis, crisis responses);
2. Information on the dependent variable (innovativeness and adaptiveness);
3. Information on the independent variables (MLG, hybridity, societal intelligence).

Within the COVID-19 pandemic, the data collection template included a national level analysis as well as a more detailed focus through two mini-cases per partner countries. The selection of the mini-cases was connected with the policy measures that were common amongst the countries experiencing the Covid-19 pandemic. The policy measures chosen for the mini-cases revolved around *school closures*, and *vaccination promotion*. Both highlight prominent policy measures that were implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic and reflected the ability of governments to adjust to meet the new challenges (Boin et al., 2021).

Altogether 19 mini-cases in school closures and vaccination promotion and admissions were prepared, for which 108 interviews were conducted. Interviewees included representatives of national, regional and local public sector decisionmakers; public health agency manager; politicians/administrators in central government; civil society organization staff; experts and task force members; journalists having covered the relevant mini-case. The recruitment of interviewees was carried out with gender balance in mind. This provided a more comprehensive picture of the empirical examples, which enabled to better understand the linkages between the relevant factors. The mini-cases chosen varied from local to regional to national level, which enabled to better comprehend the factors relevant in different levels in both horizontal and vertical interactions. Such rich data allowed to explore and further theorize on the linkages between societal intelligence and robustness, as presented in this deliverable analysis.

Whilst the WP3-5 data gathering template provided access to primary data, this remained limited in depth, which ruled out the possibility of conducting a robust comparative analysis. The data collected was utilized to complement existing theoretical insight and explore new potential

dynamics or connections between societal intelligence and robustness. As a result, the analysis does not elaborate on the relevance or strength of specific factors, but rather provides an explorative overview of the potential factors. These linkages will be further studied in WP6, which conducts an in-depth empirical analysis.

Conditions for the development of societal intelligence in knowledge interfaces

Before delving into the conditions leading to build societal intelligence in interfaces, it is relevant to discuss what the impact of such intelligence would be on the governance of a crisis. Literature on information processing highlights that the reciprocal transfer of information is conducive to a “rapid and effective innovative response” (Philipps et al., 2023, p.193), and that citizens and other actors beyond the government possess different views and valuable information that helps shape those innovative responses (Bourgon, 2009). Similarly, scholars working on knowledge exchange underline that approaches based on co-production and adaptive learning would bring forward better outcomes in decision-making, both in effectiveness and durability (Fazey et al., 2012).

Drawing on this literature, we may tentatively assume that in times of crisis high levels of societal intelligence will enable high levels of robust governance and, conversely, low levels of societal intelligence will impede robust governance. The logic here is that societal intelligence expands the space for the ways in which crises are understood and how they may be governed. By expanding the knowledge interface to include not only politics and expertise but also lifeworld knowledge, the risk of adopting governance solutions that overlook fundamental civil society concerns is likely to be reduced. In Belgium, for instance, public authorities, teacher unions, schools, and parent representatives engaged in intense dialogue to handle the ways in which schools were closed and reopened in order to minimize the negative impact on children regarding their learning and mental wellbeing. The stakeholders were motivated to take part in such consultations, as they perceived they were impacting change, and their voices were heard.

Conversely, if lifeworld knowledge is ignored, the government risks underplaying the role of local conditions and everyday concerns that may influence the robustness of governance solution. In Hungary, for instance, the early launch of a vaccination program during the pandemic was not successful in the sense that vaccination rates were quite low compared to most other EU countries. This may have to do with a very closed decision-making process where medical experts other than the ones from the Ministry of Health were not consulted. In fact, public debate, including that of university experts, was muted by the government via its control over the major national broadcasting services. The low uptake of vaccines may have contributed to Hungary’s relatively high mortality rates during the second wave of the pandemic.

Inclusivity

Inclusivity refers to the degree different knowledge types – political, expert, and lifeworld knowledge – have access to the interface. This is not based on the number of actors involved, but on the variation in the types of knowledge individual actors bring to the table (Table 1). The condition of inclusivity is derived from research on cognitive diversity (Landemore, 2012), claiming that such diversity of interpretive and predictive models in a group would allow for better problem-solving. Dinesh (2023) also makes a case in point in his chapter on crowdsourcing. When discussing the “Smarter Crowdsourcing in the Age of Coronavirus” case, he underlines how crucial it was to have diversified expertise in order to have more innovative ideas, capable of tackling global problems.

In brief, the more diverse the knowledge brought to the table, the higher the ability to transform this knowledge into action – i.e., intelligence – by producing relevant and effective solutions. In general, then, we would expect a crisis situation to negatively affect the condition of inclusivity. As the handling of a crisis often requires swift and unambiguous action, it is tempting for

policymakers to narrow down the number of actors participants in the decision-making process to a minimum, such as key experts and key members of the major political parties in parliament. However, the crisis also offers an opportunity to include actors that are not normally part of decision-making, such as private companies, interest organizations, civil society groups or experts as they possess knowledge or other resources deemed essential to handle the crisis.

Productive contestation

Our notions of productive and unproductive contestation draw on political theorist Chantal Mouffe's distinction between agonist and antagonist conflict (Mouffe, 1999). Agonist conflict reflects a situation in which two or more parties disagree and try to win a battle but do so within agreed rules and norms. That is, while the conflicting parties do not necessarily reach an agreement, they try to solve their differences by respecting each other by, for instance, accepting not to lie or not to ridicule each other. This dual understanding of contestation has proven useful to handle differences of knowledge at play in the context of innovation and planning (Valkenburg, 2020; Pløger, 2017).

Productive contestation is a condition that is not easily met. Striving for inclusivity of knowledge types may increase the uncertainty and the messiness of the information available (Dahlmann & Roehrich, 2019) if the knowledge is not negotiated or contested in a productive manner. In the case of expert knowledge, often linked to its certainty and trustworthiness, its inflationary use can also cause more uncertainty (Bäckstrand, 2003) if not paired with an understanding of the underlying epistemology and productive contestation of its limits. Such conflicts may easily turn out to be unproductive in the sense that some points of view are regarded as illegitimate or that some actors are more interested in airing their frustrations and convincing other actors than in listening and contributing to governance solutions that most actors will regard as acceptable. In times of crisis, by allowing for all three forms of knowledge, it is almost inevitable that some kind of conflict will emerge about how to understand the crisis, its causes, its consequences and how best to deal with it.

In general, contestation in crisis situations involves the articulation of dissenting interests and points of view and the negotiation over which forms of knowledge are considered legitimate when debating how a crisis should be governed. Productive contestation here refers to the situation where actors acknowledge the legitimacy of understandings of a crisis that differ from their own, and strive to resolve, albeit not eliminate, such differences. Such an acknowledgment of different understandings may, in turn, allow for the formulation of wider strategies and perhaps even more specific policies for governing the crisis. In contrast, unproductive contestation is the situation in which some actors refuse to engage with the arguments and types of knowledge voiced by other actors. They may even go as far as to ridicule the other actors and depict them as stupid or malevolent.

Self-efficacy

Self-efficacy refers to the perception of actors participating in the interface that their contribution via knowledge exchange is meaningful and will have an impact on policy outcomes. Literature on self-efficacy indicates that the amount of effort and time people will devote and the chances of them engaging in political participation are directly affected by beliefs about self-efficacy (Caprara et al., 2009; Lieberman & Zhou, 2022; Solhaug, 2006). Such beliefs are "crucial to any action" (Solhaug, 2006, p.269), and self-efficacy can in fact help us make sense of the link between knowledge and action (Bandura, 1982; Lieberman & Zhou, 2022).

We define here self-efficacy as "a person's sense of being capable of affecting change" (Lieberman & Zhou 2022, p.48 based on Bandura, 1977). This can be further specific into internal and external efficacy, reflecting one's abilities and competence on the one hand and the responsiveness of the institutions on the other. What is even more relevant to our study of societal intelligence is the conceptualization of internal political efficacy (Campbell et al., 1954). This concept examines whether one believes they can achieve the desired result through political engagement, thus playing a crucial role in determining political participation.

In the case of interfaces and crises such as COVID-19, with deep uncertainty and conflicting values, we ask ourselves what would lead actors to exchange their knowledge and avoid strategic uses of it (Van Enst et al., 2014). Knowledge could in fact be deliberately ignored, selectively used, produced in an incomplete way, or disqualified through counter arguments.

Research on deliberative policymaking in Taiwan during COVID-19 (Liu & Lin, 2023) reveals that allowing people to influence the agenda on issues that concern them enhances how much they value the outcomes and ultimately the resilience of society in the face of the pandemic. Put differently, by including lifeworld knowledge early in decision-making processes, it is possible to produce governance solutions that address the needs and harness the capacities of target groups. In other words, self-efficacy entails involving actors in interfaces in a way and at a stage that makes them believe they are capable of affecting change. Doing so is likely to produce a higher quality of knowledge exchange, as the actors will be more motivated and will pool their knowledge, competencies and resources to solve the problem at hand (Caprara et al., 2009). Self-efficacy could also show how inclusivity might not be sufficient to build intelligence during a crisis but underline the need for responsiveness to the engagement of actors.

Intensity

Intensity refers to the recurrence of the interface configuration. This entails that a group of actors interact more or less regularly over time. In contrast to one-time or very irregular meetings, regular interactions are conducive to learning and, ultimately, to the production of intelligence (e.g. Colom et al., 2010). This is also related to the condition productive contestation described above. One way to make contestation productive is in fact to have enough time to embrace the “rules of the game” of a certain interface, i.e. the way things are discussed and the norms regulating behavior. In that way, alternative opinions can be voiced within these working practices, allowing for negotiated interaction. Heightened intensity also allows actors to make sense of other’s knowledge types with their corresponding epistemological logics.

Employing organizational learning theory, Deverell (2010; 2022) argues that crises can induce learning, both in terms of knowledge – i.e. having a new understanding – and in terms of behavior. If this happens within the crisis episode, we can talk about *intra-crisis learning*. Such learning is essential for crisis management as the general public expects that policymakers and government authorities learn from failures and experiences (Deverell, 2022).

Following this understanding, we expect recurring interfaces configurations to allow for feedback on the measures taken to tackle crisis challenges, thus providing new understandings of the dynamics at hand and possibly leading to policy adjustments. Such a process would thus denote intra-crisis learning and produce more robust and reliable solutions.

Adaptability

Adaptability refers to the ability of an interface to adapt. This could involve a change of the actor composition in the knowledge interface, in the frequency of interactions, in the short- or long-term goals, in the degree of formality, or in the boundary objects produced, such as reports, communication materials, indicators, and recommendations. Such adaptations can take place when the goals of the interface change, or at times of political turnover, where some administrations might adjust to new leadership visions.

Crisis times call for adaptability. Crises often entail dealing with unstructured problems for which there is no definite solution, there’s a need for credible, salient, and legitimate knowledge (Van Enst et al., 2014). An adaptable interface can work towards fulfilling this need, providing the necessary knowledge as the crisis unfolds and produces at times unanticipated consequences.

For instance, the temporary school closures during the pandemic created unprecedented challenges to student learning and mental wellbeing. This called for pedagogical and psychological expertise and the inclusion of stakeholders such as parents, students (in the case of higher education), teachers unions, and school directors in order to design new educational formats, such as outdoor teaching, or measures to cope with the spread of the virus and its effect on children.

National-level responses

The COVID-19 crisis appears to be a fertile ground to study developments in knowledge exchange and interface formation within a crisis. This is especially because of the shifting in the crisis framing, from a mere health crisis since the global pandemic declaration by the WHO to the attention given to economic and social consequences of the crisis then included in crisis management measures.

Based on the conditions just presented, the analysis of the national-level responses shows interesting trends and single cases relevant to the knowledge angle of crisis governance. These results highlight the different pathways possible to build societal intelligence in times of crisis and which configurations led to robust crisis solutions (see sidebar note). These are discussed in the following paragraphs.

Robust governance configurations

Configuration 1: self-efficacy + intensity or adaptability

The first configuration emerging from multiple national responses sees interfaces combining self-efficacy and intensity or adaptability. Thus, perceiving to be capable of affecting change through the knowledge exchange in a certain interface, together with repeated interactions with that same configuration or adapting some interface features through the crisis, led to the creation of robust solutions.

This was mainly the case for expert-based groups, which as an interface were not championing inclusivity. However, they were clearly affecting change, as their recommendations were often followed to the letter by the national governments.

A clear illustration of this mechanism was the ad-hoc advisory group set up in Denmark, made up of five experts between economists and virologists. Their role was to give advice to the government regarding the reopening of societal activities, and their influence on government policy was substantial. This interface displays high self-efficacy, but also relatively high adaptability as the group updated its strategies for reopening based on a broad range of scientific evidence and modeling.

The advice of the Scientific Advisory Board in Estonia was also closely followed by the national government, making it a similar case of political-expert knowledge interface with high self-efficacy. However, in this case, self-efficacy went hand in hand with intensity, as the interface was meeting weekly – allowing for continuous feedback and intra-crisis learning.

Similarly, the Outbreak Management Team (OMT) in the Netherlands was an interface composed of medical experts set up after the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic. This team gave elucidations of the pandemic trends and met weekly at peak times. The national government consulted this interface continuously, thus heavily relying on expert knowledge. The capacity of this interface to affect change can be undoubtedly deduced from the debate on whether or not wearing face masks should be mandatory. Even though other countries used the facemasks from an early stage of the COVID-19 crisis, the OMT disputed their effectiveness. Consequently, wearing facemasks was not made obligatory in the Netherlands in the beginning of the pandemic.

While these configurations did provide robust solutions at a certain stage of the crisis – also given the high public trust in government and expert bodies in some countries – such limited inclusivity

Robust governance configurations

Configuration 1: self-efficacy + intensity or adaptability

Configuration 2: inclusivity + adaptability + productive contestation

Configuration 3: inclusivity + intensity + self-efficacy

Configuration 4: inclusivity + adaptability + intensity

Configuration 5: inclusivity + adaptability

run the risk of overlooking fundamental civil society concerns, that only a broader knowledge base can bring to the table. For example, as the COVID-19 crisis prolonged, critiques were raised in the Netherlands regarding the OMT. The lack of participation of experts from the social sciences, especially to discuss the impact of school closures on children, was one of the criticisms. In response to this, the “Red Team C19 NL” was created, composed of an independent group of people in different fields that critically evaluated policies and strategies and, thereby, offered interdisciplinary advice.

It was thus through other configurations that societal intelligence was built and robust crisis solutions came about from such knowledge negotiation. As anticipated, inclusivity appears to be a precondition for building societal intelligence. Several pathways to adaptation and innovation within crisis governance include an interface where multiple knowledge types are included. These inclusive options are discussed in the following paragraphs.

Configuration 2: inclusivity + adaptability + productive contestation

Including a variety of voices that reflect different knowledge types and underlying epistemologies can be especially important for robustness when it comes to hard-to-reach groups and close-knit communities.

In such cases, productive contestation seems an essential condition to build societal intelligence and robust solutions to the crisis, together with inclusivity and adaptability of the interface. The illustration mirroring this configuration comes from the Netherlands, and more specifically from a small city characterized by a close-knit, traditional, and family-oriented way of life. The residents often have strong family ties and the local dialect is still spoken by many of them. Religion also plays a crucial role in the life of the residents, and the majority of the population adheres to the strict Reformed Protestant tradition, a conservative Calvinist denomination that emphasizes strict adherence to religious doctrine and traditions.

Coupled with the spread of misinformation and general distrust in scientific knowledge and government, the authorities faced difficulties in enforcing the national guidelines. The robustness of this case lies in the balancing act of protecting basic functions and goals while also maintaining strong community values and leaving room for a diversity of perspectives. This was achieved through a combination of inclusivity, adaptability, and productive contestation.

The national government's communication and vaccination strategy did not match the local needs and demands of this local community. Thus, the local government felt compelled to offer an alternative and initiated a television show streamed on YouTube, adapting the framing and the communication. In this show, both GPs and religious leaders participated, making it an interface inclusive of different types of knowledge, with clear diverse underlying epistemologies. This variety of voices and experiences was crucial in order to reach the population and communicate about the vaccine, improving their knowledge base for decision-making. More importantly, these actors shared their views during the show with respect, without ridiculing the other or proving their illegitimacy – thus showcasing productive contestation.

A further feature of adaptation as a robustness strategy is the initiative taken by GPs to vaccinate within their practice. Aware of being well-known and trusted professionals, GPs – with the support of the local government – offered this service as the Delta variant started spreading and vaccination rates were still quite low in the city. Residents were in fact very much hesitant not only about the vaccine in itself but also about the large-scale locations where they were supposed to receive it – as they did not want to be seen given the anti-vaxx opinions and social control. GPs initiative thus greatly improved people's freedom of choice.

Configuration 3: inclusivity + intensity + self-efficacy

Another successful configuration sees inclusivity combined with intensity and self-efficacy. The wide consultation groups convened by the Belgian regional ministers of education are an illustration thereof. Such interfaces were created ad-hoc for the crisis and included a diverse range

of education stakeholders, such as parent representatives, teacher trade unions, psychologists, virologists, pedagogy experts, and even student representatives in the case of the Flemish region. Evidence from interviews underlines how these contacts reduced uncertainty, supported knowledge negotiation and jointly built solutions, and allowed stakeholders to provide early and continuous feedback on the measures implemented.

Such variety of actors brought a diverse range of knowledge types to the table. What made this new interface a success was on the one hand the perception of actors that the knowledge they were exchanging was impacting change in policy-making – self-efficacy – on the other, the opportunity to meet regularly – intensity – made learning and feedback on the measures coming from direct experiences possible.

An additional important insight from the interviews sheds some light on the risks of consulting with such inclusive groups. It appears that these meetings were quite long, given the amount of representatives involved, and that everyone was given a moment to present their viewpoints. Such an amount of information could potentially increase the uncertainty, getting further away from sense-making instead of closer. However, such a combination of inclusivity with intensity and self-efficacy seems to have mitigated this risk. The actors interviewed were very positive about their experience within this interface, and they indicated that their uncertainty was overall reduced through this knowledge exchange. Interestingly, an actor remarked that they decided to send written feedback instead of participating in the meeting. This not only underlines the perceived self-efficacy of the representatives but also shows that reducing information messiness can happen somewhat organically under the right conditions.

Configuration 4: inclusivity + adaptability + intensity

In other cases, inclusivity combined with intensity and adaptability also spurred the development of societal intelligence and resulted in robust crisis solutions. The municipality governments in Estonia had regular meetings with the Health Board, which resulted in developing trust-based relationships. Based on the outbreaks, heads of schools were engaged as well, thus adapting the member composition of the interface. Expert, political, and lifeworld knowledge were in such a way all included. This collaboration, while formalized, was still coordinated in an ad hoc manner, with ties intensifying during peak moments and activated based on needs – denoting both intensity and adaptability.

Another illustration from national responses that mirrors such a successful configuration is the consultation and collaboration structures regarding schools and education at the local level in the Netherlands. While this interface already existed before the crisis, the COVID-19 pandemic was an opportunity to upscale such a structure. Consultation became more regular, peaking at weekly (online) meetings.

All different knowledge types were included in this interface, brought to the table by representatives of the municipality government, youth care, child care services, school directors, voluntary organizations, and at times private actors, too. The knowledge input from these actors helped create a broader strategy to support children and their education, and was regarded as complementary: professionals from the education sector knew how the measures would play out in their school setting, while youth care experts could add their insights from the health and safety point of view. Interviewees also underlined learning from each other as an essential and useful feature of such knowledge exchanges.

The inclusion of new partners into the discussion for specific issues is evidence of the adaptability of the interface. An example thereof is the inclusion of banks when the provision of laptops for distance learning was discussed. Such inclusivity, intensity, and adaptability produced crisis solutions that were perceived as legitimate.

Configuration 5: inclusivity + adaptability

Inclusivity and adaptability are present in multiple robust configurations enabling societal intelligence to build up. In some cases, it appears that these two conditions together might be

sufficient to co-create robust governance solutions based on a broader knowledge base and mirroring the deepest societal needs and concerns.

Two illustrations from the Netherlands and Belgium depict such a configuration. The Dutch case includes an interface between medical specialists, GPs, and community leaders to reach vulnerable groups within a city characterized by a diverse multi-ethnic community. The area had historically faced e.g. poverty and social inequality, and when COVID hit public leaders realized that patients from vulnerable neighborhoods ended up in the hospital more often and were not getting vaccinated. Given the common challenges, frontline professionals initiated, together with community leaders, a local information and vaccination strategy at weekly local markets that was targeted at vulnerable groups.

This inclusive interface was thus relying both on expert and lifeworld knowledge. In addition to inclusivity, this interface also showcased the adaptability of its goals and boundary objects. Firstly, they adapted their information materials to the local circumstances and made them accessible and available at the weekly local markets. Secondly, this interface adapted its initial goal from mere information supply to vaccination provision during the crisis. Frontline professionals and community actors had in fact noticed that people often decided to get a vaccine after they received the information, and would want it right away. Thus, navigating both legal and practical obstacles, this goal adaptation took place.

The success of this case is also explained through the reliance on volunteers and local intermediaries, who made it possible to gain trust among citizens – the same vulnerable ones that because of a combination of misinformation, distrust in government, and practical barriers, were not getting their vaccination beforehand.

The reliance on the local network of intermediaries and volunteers also characterizes the Belgian case. Health councils leading first-line zones at the local level in Belgium proved essential to tackle vaccine hesitancy and having an overview of the development of the crisis. Overseeing delimited and clearly defined geographical areas within the Flemish region, such councils constituted an inclusive interface. Their membership included in fact primary healthcare providers, local authorities, insurance companies, and user associations – thus a mix of public and private actors, representing political, expert, and lifeworld knowledge.

Thanks to this varied knowledge exchanged during the pandemic, they contributed to the management of the crisis by controlling outbreaks and raising awareness about vaccination through customized information. This showcases the adaptability of the interface, both in terms of boundary objects – as again the information was adapted to the local circumstances – and to the different phases of the crisis, acting upon emerging outbreaks and tackling them ad-hoc.

Summary of findings

This research has identified five conditions that enable the development of societal intelligence in knowledge interfaces. These are inclusivity, productive contestation, self-efficacy, intensity, and adaptability. Analyzing the national-level responses during the COVID-19 crisis, certain configurations of such conditions have emerged. The combinations of conditions, e.g. self-efficacy together with intensity or inclusivity together with adaptability, appear to have spurred robust crisis solutions while allowing the development of a more or less broad knowledge base. These successful configurations are summarized here.

Self-efficacy, intensity or adaptability. In countries such as Estonia, Denmark, and the Netherlands, expert groups with limited inclusivity were still very successful in impacting policy change by advising national governments. This self-efficacy, combined with the intensity of their meetings or the adaptability of their scientific modeling, allowed this interface configuration to deliver robust governance solutions at that point in time. However, as the case of the Netherlands highlights, lack of inclusivity can raise criticisms as the crisis prolongs – especially when the social consequences of the management measures are not contemplated.

Thus, it becomes clearer that a limited knowledge base (e.g., only expert knowledge, from one discipline) can have some drawbacks in the long-term legitimacy of its decisions, particularly when it comes to taking into account societal concerns. Such configurations did in fact not allow for societal intelligence to develop, despite producing interim robust solutions.

The next options discuss, to the contrary, configurations that combine inclusivity with the other conditions. These interfaces not only delivered robust solutions, but based them on negotiated societal intelligence.

Inclusivity, adaptability, and productive contestation. In the case of close-knit communities with e.g. adherence to specific traditions, this combination proved successful for adapting and innovating in times of crisis. In the Dutch case described above, for example, the national government's communication and vaccination strategy did not match local needs. Thus, the local government adapted their communication through a TV show, inviting a variety of voices that engaged in knowledge negotiation in a productive manner. Within the same municipality, GPs also took the initiative to vaccinate within their practice, greatly improving people's freedom of choice and showcasing adaptation.

Inclusivity, intensity, and self-efficacy. When consulting intensely with broader groups including diverse actors and knowledge types, the perception that one can affect change and the opportunity to meet regularly appear to be a recipe for success. This was the case in Belgium, with broad consultation groups regarding schools' closure. Actors felt their voice was heard and that their bottom-up feedback to the minister of education fed into the next crisis management measures. In addition, regular meetings allowed for continuous feedback and learning, and understanding of other actors' needs and limitations.

Inclusivity, adaptability, and intensity. In other cases, it was the adaptability of an inclusive and intensive interface making the difference. Estonia and the Netherlands are cases in point. In both countries, interfaces adapted their composition in order to produce more robust solutions to the crisis. On the one hand, the knowledge interface between the municipality governments and the health board in Estonia invited also heads of schools based on outbreaks. On the other, the inclusive group working on schools and education in the Netherlands not only got to consult more regularly on the topic, but also included other actors – e.g. representatives from banks – to provide input on specific issues.

Inclusivity and adaptability. Finally, in some cases, inclusivity and adaptability combined were sufficient to generate negotiated societal intelligence and robust solutions. Including political, expert, and lifeworld knowledge while adapting strategies and boundary objects of the interface was successful in the local outbreak management in the Belgian Flemish region. This configuration allowed the first lines of healthcare zones – the closest to citizens – to adapt quickly to local circumstances and provide customized information. Similarly, GPs, medical specialists, and community leaders in a Dutch case worked together to reach vulnerable groups in their city by providing adapted information and vaccinations at the local markets. Reliance on the local network of intermediaries and volunteers also characterizes both these cases.

Discussion

These findings shed light on the conditions for the development of societal intelligence and in which combinations they successfully allowed for robust solutions during the COVID-19 crisis. Some additional points for reflection will be presented in this section.

Firstly, it is worth discussing the reliance on expert knowledge, as exemplified by the first configuration including self-efficacy and intensity or adaptability. Such interfaces are often characterized by very low inclusivity, not only of knowledge types but also within expert knowledge itself, i.e. by including only some disciplines. During COVID-19, this meant inviting in these knowledge interfaces medical professionals, as epidemiologists. Previous sections have

already underlined that the solutions produced by such an interface run the risk of overlooking essential societal concerns given the restricted knowledge base, and received criticism for their narrow focus.

Beyond this point of criticism, the validation seminar of the ROBUST project¹ also provided further input for this discussion. First of all, who can become an expert in our societies? While there are different ways through which an expert is recognized as such (e.g. qualifications, acknowledgment by the peer community), it is essential to underline that the expertise mobilized for the pandemic has often been epistemically narrow. This also implies that some actors, carriers of other knowledge types and underlying epistemologies, have been excluded from contributing to sense-making and crisis management.

This understanding is mirrored in the findings just presented, and can be further unpacked in terms of crisis framing. In the case of COVID-19, the framing of the crisis as a health matter caused the first consultation and expert committees to be composed mostly or only of professionals from that field. It was only later on, when the economic and social repercussions of such a crisis and management measures were better understood, that knowledge interfaces became more inclusive. This discussion denotes a certain epistemic injustice (Fricker, 2007) which “at the height of the pandemic, created credibility and intelligibility deficits” (Mormina, 2022).

Secondly, it appears that the conditions of inclusivity, intensity, and adaptability are repeatedly present in robust configurations. This confirms some of our initial expectations. Inclusivity directly reflects the composition of the interface in terms of knowledge types and diversity. Thus, if an interface is characterized by inclusivity, its knowledge base is broader – which can be considered a precondition for building societal intelligence. From the analysis of our ROBUST national cases, combining inclusivity with intensity and adaptability appears as the configuration with the most chances of providing robust crisis solutions based on negotiated societal intelligence.

Thus, a successful knowledge interface is (a) composed of actors bringing to the table diverse knowledge types; (b) meeting repeatedly in time to allow for continuous feedback on the measures and intra-crisis learning; and (c) is ready to adapt with its output, goals, or even composition to the needs of the community it is serving.

The condition of intensity also implies that the actors involved in the knowledge interface also have time to understand where the others’ points of view originate and their limitations – thus the others’ epistemologies. These epistemologies underlie how one perceives and assesses the crisis and the measures or amendments one would like to introduce. Reaching such an understanding of the other actors could greatly reduce conflict, and enable more constructive and efficient knowledge negotiation and co-production of solutions.

Thirdly, while there are good theoretical reasons to believe that, in general, high levels of societal intelligence are conducive to robust governance, empirical cases demonstrate that this link is not always so straightforward.

In Belgium, for instance, the government developed a track-and-trace app to assist the tracing of the spread of the coronavirus. The app would also assist government authorities in making more targeted interventions of self-isolation and selective closures of institutions. However, despite the high inclusivity within expert knowledge and the multiple intense consultations including lifeworld knowledge, this app resulted in a failure, as only 22% of the Belgian population was using it by April 2021. The concerns raised in these feedback rounds could in fact not be incorporated in the final version of the app, as these would have undermined its rationale and utility within the crisis, thus resulting in a tool with low legitimacy and user base.

¹ This seminar took place online on April 30th, 2024, mirroring task T5.3: testing of empirical findings in discussion with stakeholders.

This example demonstrates that we need to be cautious in drawing the link between societal intelligence and robust governance and that there are other factors at play in turning negotiated societal intelligence into adaptive and innovative crisis solutions. Within the ROBUST project, such supplementary explanations can be found in the variables of multi-level governance and hybridity, which offer additional frameworks for understanding the attainment of robust crisis governance.

Finally, a conclusive point of discussion relates to the level of analysis of the ROBUST cases. While some of the interfaces described were formed at the national level, others were regional or local. On the one hand, this is a limitation of this analysis, as there is no consistency in the level of governance being analyzed. On the other, the division of competencies regarding healthcare or education in some countries played a significant role in the data collection choices.

The positive aspect of this variation in the cases is that it also allows to reflect on which configurations worked best at what level of governance. It appears that the knowledge interfaces at the regional and local levels were the most inclusive and adaptive ones, both to the changing crisis issues and to the needs of the different population groups. On the contrary, examples from the national level were expert-based bodies that affect change but lack a broader knowledge base. This finding, while somewhat not surprising, represents a point of learning for the next crises.

EU-level responses

Transboundary crises, by “jumping geographical borders and policy boundaries” (Boin et al., 2014, p.420), act as catalysts for institutional renegotiation, accelerating and consolidating changes in policy areas that had already been layering for some time (Deruelle & Engeli, 2021). At the European Union (EU) level, COVID-19 has been such catalyst and critical juncture: policymakers were faced with extraordinary uncertainty, thus opening up the possibility to bring about innovative change (Wolff & Ladi, 2020).

This has to be contextualized within the field of health policy. EU competences in this regard are spelled out in the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU), which defines the protection and improvement of human health as a *supporting competence* (art. 6 TFEU), and common safety concerns in public health matters as a *shared competence* (art. 4TFEU). Article 168 TFEU further defines the shared competence regarding public health between the EU and its Member States (see sidebar note on public health). Such arrangement has made authors define public health as an ambiguous policy area (Klika, 2021) or a very marginal one, where there is no established role for the EU in health policy (Brooks et al., 2023). At the same time, this represents also an opportunity to reflect on the drivers of integration (Brooks et al., 2023; Schmidt, 2020) in such a textbook case of cross-border externalities (Brooks et al., 2023).

Thus, the EU was in this sense “limited by design” in its crisis response (Schmidt, 2020, p.1180). Despite this, authors have framed COVID-19 as an existential crisis for the Union,

Public health

Under Article 168 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, public health is a competence shared between the European Union and its Member States. While Member States define and deliver their national health services and medical care, the EU seeks to complement national policies by means of its health strategy to:

- prevent illness/disease by promoting healthier lifestyles;
- facilitate access to better and safer healthcare;
- contribute to innovative, efficient and sustainable health systems;
- deal with cross-border threats;
- keep people healthy throughout their lifetimes;
- harness new technologies and practices.

Source: [Public health - EUR-Lex \(europa.eu\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legislation/sidebars/public_health_en.html)

threatening the EU project (Brooks et al., 2023; Ladi & Wolff, 2021; Renda & Castro, 2020). Others argued in fact that in the current state of *permanent emergency*, the EU is called to deliver an adequate response (Ladi & Wolff, 2021; Wolff & Ladi, 2020).

Was the EU able to deliver such a response? And on what knowledge was this response built?

Agencies in the spotlight and inter-crisis learning

“In the coronavirus crisis, EU member states are a bit like people — first instinct is to act for themselves, then they realise the value of good neighbours”² (Home Affairs Commissioner Ylva Johansson, March 2020).

This quote from the Home Affairs Commission Ylva Johansson from March 2020 illustrates well what was taking place at the time. Member States were resorting to measures within the boundaries of their nation states, making scholars wonder the EU level responses where (Jordana & Triviño-Salazar, 2020). However, despite an initial delay, Member States chose a more unified approach (Cavaleri et al., 2021) and the EU delivered its response and was able to adapt and innovate, and even break path dependencies in domains including health (Schmidt, 2020). Other authors describe this as a shift from coercive Europeanization to coordinative Europeanization, and define the latter as “a bottom-up process where the member states are actively involved in the policy-making process early on in order to guarantee the highest level of implementation possible” (Ladi & Wolff, 2021, p.32).

Given the centrality of coordination, EU agencies received exceptional visibility and direct public attention, both regarding their role and their messages on COVID-19 (EFSA et al., 2022; Müller & Fraussen 2023). Along key EU institutions such as the European Commission, two agencies were highly involved in the management of the crisis: the European Center for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) and the European Medicines Agency (EMA) (Forman & Mossialos, 2021; Ladi & Wolff, 2021).

EU decentralized agencies are expert-based bodies and represent the backbone of the regulatory activity of the Union. Their information-gathering and networking functions provide coordination structures between the national and the supranational level as well as among national authorities. It was because of that need for cooperation and for a “coordinated provision of expertise” (Hofmann & Morini, 2012, p.6) that these bodies proliferated since the 1990s and that they were in the spotlight as the COVID-19 crisis hit.

As expert-based bodies, the scientific and independent knowledge produced by such bodies has been of high value in supporting EU decision-making through the years. This

European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control

Operational since: 2005

Mandate reinforced in the following areas:

- epidemiological surveillance via integrated systems enabling real-time surveillance;
- preparedness and response planning, reporting and auditing;
- provision of non-binding recommendations and options for risk management;
- capacity to mobilize and deploy an EU Health Task Force to assist local response in the Member States;
- building a network of EU reference laboratories and a network for substances of human origin.

Source: [Carriages preview | Legislative Train Schedule \(europa.eu\)](#)

² Politico, EU Confidential Podcast. Episode: Coronavirus edition #2. <https://open.spotify.com/episode/4IABapYfgC4Mqcf6XWf7ox?si=27c0db3154fb4bac>

knowledge angle is also what makes these bodies highly interesting for the present research on societal intelligence.

When confronted with a crisis such as COVID-19 with so high levels of information asymmetry and equivocality (Dahlmann & Roehrich, 2019; Philipps et al., 2023), it is not surprising that the eyes turned to the ECDC in search of answers.

ECDC had indeed the most applicable mandates matching with the sub-issues of COVID-19, and was producing and sharing information on a high variety of topics related to the crisis, including early information on the outbreak, general medical information about the disease, hygiene recommendations, risk assessments, and data updates (Müller & Fraussen 2023).

Since the beginning of the pandemic, ECDC recommendations on risk management were highly requested both by the Commission and by Member States, and became also very valued by these actors (Deruelle & Engeli 2021). The advice requested ranged from guidance on health systems contingency planning to address possible containment scenarios to monitoring the implementation of EU recommendations and guidelines on testing (Deruelle & Engeli, 2021). In addition, ECDC was also involved in EU Home Affairs meetings and attended regular meetings with a global network of major CDCs (Forman & Mossialos, 2021). Thus, while its official mandate only included risk assessment, ECDC gradually gained tasks and influence on the risk management of the crisis.

The other agency in the spotlight was the European Medicines Agency. The EMA has worked regularly together with the ECDC during the COVID-19 crisis, especially when it came to monitoring the effectiveness of the vaccines receiving its conditional market authorization (CMA). In addition to the ECDC, the EMA also coordinate with the national immunization technical groups to explore its regulatory views and stay up to date regarding national vaccination strategies (Cavaleri et al., 2021).

Member States had in fact decided for a more robust strategy when it came to vaccination procurement, denoting inter-crisis learning and coordinative Europeanization already during the first phase of the crisis. The centralization of vaccination procurement stands absolutely in contrast with the strategy adopted during the swine flu pandemic, when Member States were competing with each other for vaccines and were played by vaccine manufacturers (Becker & Gehring 2023; Wolff & Ladi 2020).

Mirroring the shift in national preferences regarding health integration and the ongoing demand on the two EU agencies, the European Commission formalized these developments in practice through some legislative proposals whose end goal is the establishment of a European Health Union³ (EHU) (Becker & Gehring, 2023; Deruelle & Engeli, 2021). Building on this renewed political commitment by Member States (Wolff & Ladi, 2020), the Commission's proposals focused on public health and have today become a reality. This legislative package includes an expansion in the formal powers both of the ECDC and of the EMA, whose founding regulations⁴ have been

European Medicines Agency

Operational since: 1995

Mandate reinforced in the following areas:

- monitoring and mitigating the risk of shortages of critical medicines and medical devices;
- providing scientific advice on medicines that may have the potential to treat, prevent or diagnose the diseases causing those crises;
- coordinating studies to monitor the effectiveness and safety of vaccines;
- coordinating clinical trials.

Source: [Carriages preview | Legislative Train Schedule \(europa.eu\)](#)

³ [European Health Union - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

⁴ [Regulation - 2022/123 - EN - EUR-Lex \(europa.eu\)](#) and [Regulation - 2022/2370 - EN - EUR-Lex \(europa.eu\)](#).

formally amended. In addition, the Commission set up the European Health Emergency Preparedness and Response Authority (HERA) and the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA), that works on the implementation of funding schemes also in the health domain. These developments exemplify a re-prioritization of health within the EU (Forman & Mossialos, 2021), which was already represented by the inclusion of EU4Health in the 2021-2027 financial framework by the European Commission instead of dissolving the Health Programme (Brooks et al., 2023). Furthermore, these integration steps within public health at the EU level also underline a breaking with past path dependencies, where EU institutions and agencies were left with no additional capacities despite the precedent crises (Schmidt, 2020).

The following section will reflect more specifically on the variable of societal intelligence and how such intelligence was built – if so – through EU agencies in order to innovate for the crisis and produce robust solutions.

Building societal intelligence: adaptability, self-efficacy, and intensity

From a knowledge perspective, EU agencies can be categorized as *boundary organizations*. Boundary organizations are organizations allowing for science-policy interactions, involving actors from both sides and having distinct lines of accountability to both the world of science and politics. To reach the goal of knowledge brokerage, i.e. facilitating a two-way communication between science and policymaking, these organizations provide services such as policy analyses and evaluations, compilations of scientific data, networking, consulting, and other *boundary objects* like indicator systems and models (Clar & Steurer, 2016; Hoppe et al., 2013). Taking into account the ECDC and the EMA, it is easy to recognize these features as they represent the organization structures and services of all EU agencies⁵.

As (science-policy) knowledge interfaces, it is possible to recognize some of the conditions outlined and discussed in the national level responses also for these EU agencies.

Adaptation. The two agencies have highly adapted as interfaces during the COVID-19 crisis. Firstly, there has been a change in the tasks and thus boundary objects produced. The ECDC was given the responsibility by the Commission to advice on matters of risk management, such as reporting on the readiness of national crisis emergency systems (Deruelle & Engeli, 2021). ECDC was also successively involved in Home Affairs meetings at the EU level, which was a new arena where to share its expert input. Similarly, ECDC was now participating in gatherings of the global CDCs network that was set up just before the pandemic. At the same time, EMA worked under high time pressure in order to grant the conditional marketing authorizations (CMAs) for COVID-19 vaccines, collaborating with regulators outside the EU, the EU, and the International Coalition of Medicines Regulatory Authorities (Cavaleri et al., 2021).

An additional instance of adaptation regards the agencies' mandate. In November 2020, roughly one year after the start of the pandemic, the Commission proposed the new legislative package underlying the EHU that also included new regulations and competences' expansion for the ECDC and the EMA. Both regulations were finally adopted in 2022.

Self-efficacy. Both the ECDC and the EMA were undoubtedly able to affect change during the COVID-19 crisis. On the one hand, the ECDC advice was very frequently requested by the Commission, and such input was very much valued. As highlighted above, this advice progressed

⁵ For an overview of current existing EU agencies, see: [EU institutions and bodies profiles | European Union \(europa.eu\)](https://european-council.europa.eu/media/e300042c-3251-4f20-b011-30689810793c/attachment_data/data/eu_institutions_and_bodies_profiles_en.pdf)

For a detailed discussion of EU agencies' features, see: M. Busuioc, M. Groenleer & J. Trondal (eds.), *The Agency Phenomenon in the European Union. Emergence, Institutionalisation and Everyday Decision-making* (Manchester University Press, 2012); M. Everson, C. Monda and E. Vos (eds.), *European Agencies in between Institutions and Member States* (Wolters Kluwer, 2014); European Parliament. Directorate General for Parliamentary Research Services. (2018). *EU agencies, common approach and parliamentary scrutiny*. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2861/656418>

from mere risk assessment to cover multiple aspects of risk management. According to Deruelle and Engeli (2021), the influence of ECDC advice on the Commission progressively increased especially on the topic of border open/closure. Given the non-binding nature of ECDC recommendations, its self-efficacy is a feature not to take for granted.

On the other, the EMA with its CMAs is a different case, as such positive opinions on market authorizations are necessary conditions for a medicine to be circulated within the European Union. Despite this case being more straightforward, it still denotes self-efficacy as an interface condition.

Intensity. This condition refers to the recurring of the same interface configuration, allowing for feedback loops and learning. As the agencies have been part of the EU executive already for some time (see sidebar notes on EMA and ECDC), they have already as organizations gone through previous crises and had the chance to apply their lessons learned to the COVID-19 pandemic. This was definitely the case for vaccine procurement and the centralization of the response, authorizing the Commission to conclude Advance Purchase Agreements (APAs) with the support of EMA. Similarly, the involvement of ECDC in coordinating risk management has been a gradual path starting with the SARS crisis in 2022 (Deruelle & Engeli, 2021).

At the same time, it is also possible to look at intensity within the COVID-19 crisis. The meetings of the ECDC with the Commission, the Health Security Committee (HSC, within DG SANTE), Member States, and other CDCs were regular. Both the ECDC and the HSC were producing weekly reports and data summaries during the years of the pandemic. The interactions of EMA with the other medicines authorities and regulators were also regular during the assessment of the vaccines for market authorization. In addition, EMA was also continuously in touch with ECDC and national advisory groups on immunization to explain its views and keep up to date with their strategies. From this example, it is possible to extrapolate the support in sense-making that EMA and ECDC provided to national authorities.

Intensity and productive contestation. These two conditions do not directly emerge when analyzing the EU level response. As in some national cases discussed above, the Commission and MS relied on expert-based bodies in order to reduce their uncertainty and receive guidance regarding crisis management. Given this uncertainty and the non-binding nature of the ECDC advice, the condition of productive contestation remains excluded from this analysis.

EU agencies are evidently focused on one type of knowledge, the expert one. At first glance thus one might assume an inherently low inclusivity by design. However, given the diverse tasks already within the governing of the COVID-19 pandemic, it is possible to assume within-type inclusivity, i.e. including experts from different disciplines and specializations. Beyond this, there is a clear limit to the inclusivity of such boundary organizations. While they do facilitate the communication between science and policymaking, most of these organizations are very seldomly in touch with the broader public, even if they create information campaigns directed to citizens.

Summary of findings

Given the uncertainty, information asymmetry, and need for coordination, EU agencies whose mandate overlapped with the policy areas affected by the COVID-19 pandemic quickly found themselves receiving unprecedented attention from the public.

At this point during the crisis, despite the limits of their mandates and of the EU competences in health policy, the European Medicines Agency and the European Center for Disease Prevention and Control risked major reputational damage and were set to prove their relevance as actors to their principals (Müller & Fraussen 2023).

Notwithstanding challenges of data collection⁶, understaffing, and time pressure, EMA and especially ECDC appeared as the “rising star of the governance system for health threats management in the EU” (Deruelle & Engeli, 2021, p.1392). Their recommendations, binding or not, directly affected EU level crisis management.

The COVID-19 crisis response at the EU level also denotes instances of inter-crisis learning. The main illustration thereof regards vaccine procurement. During the swine flu outbreak in 2009, EU MS were “played off against each other by vaccine manufacturers” (Becker & Gehring, 2023, p.343). In contrast, during the COVID-19 crisis, the Commission was authorized by MS to conclude Advance Purchase Agreements with vaccine producers, thus centralizing the vaccine procurement. Finally, EU agencies can be analyzed as boundary organizations facilitating the two-way communication between science and policymaking. During the crisis, they adapted their tasks, the boundary objects they were producing, and finally also their mandate via legislative initiative by the Commission. They proved to be able to affect change through their recommendations, even when this was not binding. In addition, the intensity of their interactions with actors such as the Health and Security Committee, the MS, and other national and international regulatory authorities allowed e.g. the agencies to explain the logics behind their recommendations and regulatory decisions.

Discussion

This analysis of the EU level response to the COVID-19 crisis from a knowledge perspective also paves the way for some reflections.

Firstly, the new mandate of the ECDC, entered into force in 2022, expands the tasks of the agency to risk management. While the recommendations of the agency remain non-binding, this still qualifies as quite an important deepening step of integration. More importantly, this raises questions of legitimacy and accountability at the EU level. While such questions are not new, as democratic legitimacy has always been the Achille’s heel of the Union, it is still worth discussing this theme within this research.

As underlined by Paccès and Weimer (2020), scientific risk assessors do not possess neither democratic legitimacy nor political responsibility. Scientific advice remains an essential element of crisis management, but risk managers carry a political responsibility towards their society which EU agencies do not enjoy. For example, public leaders at the national, regional, and local level are aware of what their communities are willing to accept as risk and what kind of precautions they would prefer.

Such decentralized risk management is deemed the most efficient, and the most democratically legitimate, mirroring the principle of subsidiarity⁷. This also explains why, despite receiving the same recommendations from the EU level, MS adopted at times diverse strategies to deal with the pandemic as this mirrored their risk cultures. As an illustration, Sweden and the Netherlands were the least strict countries when it came to lockdowns and other restrictive measures.

Secondly, the COVID-19 crisis has prompted paradigmatic change in health policy at the EU level. On the one hand, EU competences are clear and remain only supporting to the action of MS (articles 4, 6, 168 TFEU). Given this limited design, no health-related crisis could have instantly created a fully integrated EU health policy. On the other, some changes have taken place: the Commission has put forward a legislative package supporting a European Health Union; ECDC and EMA have a renewed and expanded mandate; EU4Health is part of the 2021-2027 financial framework; and new bodies have been set up, such as the HERA and the HaDEA. This signals a

⁶ The data reported from the national authorities regarding the various relevant crisis indicators was not of equal quality or following the same methodologies. This proved to be a significant challenge for the ECDC. (Forman & Mossialos, 2021).

⁷ [Principle of subsidiarity - EUR-Lex \(europa.eu\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legislation/principles/subsidiarity/)

breaking of the path dependencies that left the EU level with limited capacities in this policy area (Brooks & Geyer, 2020).

Lastly, the EU has shown the capacity to adapt and react during the pandemic. Following a tense start with MS turning inward, renewed political commitment and entrepreneurship from the European Commission have allowed for inter-crisis learning and coordination among MS on certain aspects of the crisis. Health policy has been the area where these integration steps, as described in this analysis, are evident. What the EU has delivered is based on paths and institutions that had been set up before this crisis, and could then be employed and activated for crisis management (Wolff & Ladi, 2020).

Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic has proved to be a fertile ground for the study of crisis governance from a knowledge perspective. On the one hand, one of the most significant features of the pandemic governance was the involvement of experts' and their recommendations in decision-making. On the other, both private and civil society actors complained they had little or no say in the political decisions and interventions that were dramatically affecting their lives. This research looks at the triad of political expert, and lifeworld knowledge and how these knowledge types interacted during the crisis.

COVID-19 has brought turbulence to our administrative systems and societies, but also provided a window of opportunity to adapt and innovate, aiming for robust crisis solutions. According to the perspective adopted in this paper, robustness can be achieved through decisions based on a wider knowledge base, where the actors exchanging this knowledge make the effort to understand each other's underlying logic and limitations – what we have called *societal intelligence*. This research has identified five conditions that enable the development of societal intelligence in knowledge interfaces. These are inclusivity, productive contestation, self-efficacy, intensity, and adaptability. Certain configurations of these conditions appear to have spurred robust crisis solutions while allowing the development of a more or less broad knowledge base.

The analysis of national level responses has led to the identification of the following successful configurations for robust governance:

- Self-efficacy + intensity or adaptability
- Inclusivity + adaptability + productive contestation
- Inclusivity + intensity + self-efficacy
- Inclusivity + adaptability + intensity
- Inclusivity + adaptability

Given the evolving framing of the COVID-19 crisis, from a mere health focus to the attention given to economic and social consequences, different types of knowledge were requested to inform policymaking at different phases of the crisis. The reliance on expert knowledge, especially at the beginning of the crisis, is reflected for example in the first configuration where expert based committees and advisory groups were highly influential on policymaking, despite the lack of inclusiveness.

Some lessons can be learned from the COVID-19 crisis on this matter. Firstly, such low inclusivity runs the risk of overlooking essential societal concerns. Secondly, this narrow knowledge base can become the target of criticism from the broader public, especially when the ample consequences of the management measures start to emerge. This denotes a certain epistemic injustice. Some actors and knowledge types might be completely excluded, leading to deficits both in legitimacy and in credibility. At the same time, we need to ask ourselves who can become an expert in our societies, and reflect on the remaining obstacles and how to tackle them.

Hence, inclusivity can be said to be a precondition for building societal intelligence. Combining inclusivity with intensity and adaptability appears as the configuration with the most chances of providing robust crisis solutions. Thus, a successful knowledge interface is (a) composed of actors bringing to the table diverse knowledge types; (b) meeting repeatedly in time for continuous feedback on the measures and intra-crisis learning; and (c) is ready to adapt its output, goals, or even composition to the needs of the community it is serving.

An additional finding from the data collection at the national level is connected to the level of governance. The knowledge interfaces at the regional and local levels involved in crisis management were the most inclusive and adaptive ones, both to the changing crisis issues and to the needs of the different population groups. As underlined also in the literature, decentralized risk management does match the preferences and the features of a society more efficiently (Pacces & Weimer, 2020).

Moving to the European level, COVID-19 has been a catalyst for accelerating and consolidating changes that were already layering for some time, especially in the policy area of public health. While the EU was limited by design in terms of competences in this field, the pandemic has prompted what some authors have called *paradigmatic* change (Deruelle & Engeli, 2021; Schmidt, 2020; Wolff & Ladi, 2020).

The EU agencies with the most applicable mandates for this crisis, the European Center for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC) and the European Medicines Agency (EMA), received unprecedented public attention and were quickly into the spotlight given their expertise and coordination capacities. These agencies adapted their tasks, the boundary objects they were producing, and finally also their mandate via legislative initiative by the Commission. They proved to be able to affect change through their opinions and recommendations, even when non-binding. In addition, the intensity of their interactions with Member States, Commission committees and other regulatory authorities gave them the opportunity to explain the logic behind their recommendations and regulatory decisions.

The lesson learned from this experience at the EU level is that path dependencies can be broken. Despite previous crisis, such as the SARS in 2002 or the swine flu in 2009, the EU capacities within health policy had remained very limited. However, with the COVID-19 pandemic the EU has demonstrated a high level of adaptation, building on institutions and paths crafted during those crises in the last decade. Thus, while we cannot speak of a fully integrated European health policy, the legislative initiatives of the Commission towards a EHU definitely mirror a renewed political commitment in this policy field.

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